

Critical5G-Net: Addressing Critical Node Impact on Lifetime and Latency in 5G IoT Networks

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Abstract—In 5G networks, massive Internet of Things (IoT) devices pose challenges like network management and security. Such networks are vulnerable to natural phenomena and attacks due to the lack of physical protection and insufficient security mechanisms. This paper examines that not all nodes are equally affected by their incapacitation; some *critical nodes* deteriorate the most in the network performance when incapacitated. Our study investigates the effects of eliminating critical nodes on two critical network performance metrics, namely lifetime and latency, using the Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) framework. Numerical evaluations prove that these critical nodes significantly impact lifetime and latency, and their identification is essential for adjusting the service tolerance and improving network maintenance. For example, in a disk-shaped network topology scenario with 100 nodes, if two critical nodes are removed, the lifetime can decrease by 56% when minimum latency is enforced by allowing a 24% latency increase; such lifetime deterioration can be reduced to 13%.

Keywords—Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Internet of Things (IoT), 5G, critical IoT nodes, network lifetime.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Fifth Generation (5G) network is introduced to support huge and diverse types of traffic [1]. Indeed, massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) is one of the major applications of 5G which is designed to support a large number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. In 5G networks, the rapid increase in the number of IoT devices will lead towards what is being referred to as the massive IoT (mIoT) [2]. The coexistence of mIoT devices poses a challenge in terms of maximizing the overall network’s successful transmission capacity while also lowering multi-hop transmission delay in order to serve mission-critical applications. As a result, successful data transit with minimal latency from source to destination is critical for the optimal operation of mIoT devices. Despite the fact that most mIoT networks are infrastructure based, and consist of a large number of sensors called Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) which are composed of a plurality of sensor nodes distributed over a target area to be sensed and can be configured as a self-organized wireless communication network [3]. The topology of a WSN is usually composed of sensor nodes that can cooperate with neighbor nodes to transmit data to the Base Station (BS). In such a multi-hop mIoT network, careful determination of the path between nodes and sink is necessary to ensure efficient data delivery. Many different metrics can be considered to determine such paths, including latency, and lifetime.

Due to insufficient physical protection and security mechanisms, mIoT is susceptible to a variety of attacks such as Denial of Service (DoS) and natural hazards such as earthquakes, landslides, and many unanticipated risks, that can disable sensor nodes by destroying one or more sensor nodes and rendering them irreversibly inoperable. For example, sensor nodes used in intelligent transportation systems that are placed at intersections to gather real-time data on traffic flow, vehicle density, and pedestrian movement, can be targeted by malicious actors launching DoS attacks. Disrupting these sensor nodes can cause a significant deterioration in traffic management and result in congestion or accidents in cities.

Motivation. In principle, nodes may not have the same impact on network performance if they are incapacitated; some nodes are more *critical* than others. We define critical nodes differently from the literature, where elimination results in network disconnection [4], whereas we assume that the network is strongly connected, so the removal of critical nodes doesn’t mean the network is disconnected. In this paper, we are focusing on the principal subset of mIoT networks (or equivalently, WSNs) and explore two crucial performance metrics, namely the lifetime and the latency. Latency is defined here as the aggregation of end-to-end delay as the delay from the time needed to send a packet from a node to the sink and it is directly related to the number of hops to be traveled. The lifetime is measured from the moment the network starts to the point that the first sensor node runs out of energy [5].

Two reasons make it crucial to identify and evaluate critical nodes in mIoT networks [6]. The identification of critical nodes and the evaluation of their impact on mIoT networks is important for two reasons. It may not be feasible to protect all sensors against attacks and natural risks, but if only critical sensors are protected, the problem may be viable. Furthermore, the amount of maximum degradation caused by removing a given number of nodes can be useful for the design/maintenance of the network and for adjusting service tolerance.

Contributions. Our main contributions of this study are folded as:

- A general Mixed Integer Programming (MIP) optimization model to determine the critical nodes in IoT network;
- A joint latency-lifetime MIP optimization model with maximum lifetime as an objective function and a relaxation on latency minimization;

- A joint latency-lifetime MIP optimization model with latency minimization as an objective function and a relaxation on the lifetime maximization;
- Numerical evaluation of critical nodes for the derived models and their impact on performance.

II. RELATED WORK

Latency, also known as one-way delay, denotes the duration it takes for data to traverse from one point to a specific direction. The collection of data within IoT networks stems from a diverse array of sources, encompassing IoT sensors that meticulously monitor environmental conditions, alongside low-power radio-based devices, Bluetooth technologies, and actuators. These disparate data sources could be transmitted via a single-hop or multi-hop transmission relaying through intermediate nodes which comes up with the delay issue [7], [8]. In numerous research articles, the issue of minimizing latency in multi-hop IoT networks is discussed. A minimum hop routing scheme enables IoT sensor nodes to send their data to the sink through the path comprising the least number of relay nodes possible [9], [10]. Furthermore, the nodes' lifetime depends heavily on two main factors, namely the number of packets to be transmitted and the transmission range, for which numerous literature solutions are also available [11], [12]. Nonetheless, when both the lifetime and the latency are treated at the same time, previous solutions are not valid anymore [13]–[16], where there is a trade-off between minimizing the hop count and maximizing the network lifetime. To simplify the problem and find a valid solution, we can relax the minimum hop count objective, which allows packets to be spread more widely among fewer nodes [17]. This paper adopts such a relaxation strategy for both our joint models and our critical node analyses. In this paper, we use our previous works [5] and [18] as a basis and propose two joint models that, either by relaxing the minimum latency or the maximum network lifetime objectives, are able to identify the critical nodes and evaluate their impact on both metrics.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

This model uses a disk-shaped topology with a central BS (*i.e.*, the sink) and multiple sensors spread randomly across the disk [6]. The sensor nodes can transmit their own data as well as relay data to the BS from other sensor nodes. The BS receives data packets from all sensors. The network topology is represented by a directed graph, $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of all sensor nodes and the BS is defined as node n_0 . We also define a set $W = V \setminus \{n_0\}$, which includes all nodes except n_0 . $E = \{(i, j) : i \in W, j \in V \setminus \{i\}\}$ is the set of arcs in which $i \neq j$. The data traffic generated at node n_i is denoted as s_i and the data traffic from node n_i to node n_j is represented as an integer variable f_{ij} . The goal is to identify the N_c critical nodes, that is, those nodes that, once removed, cause the most significant degradation of the network's performance (latency or lifetime). To this aim, we propose a novel MIP framework and examine four different models. The first model (Section III-A) determines

TABLE I: Terminology of the MIP models

Variable	Description
f_{ij}	Flow from node- i to node- j
s_i	Data generated at node- i
d_{ij}	Distance between node- i and node- j
$G = (V, E)$	Directed graph that represents network topology
V	Set of nodes, including the BS
W	Set of nodes, except the BS
E	Set of edges
HC	Aggregated latency of the network
HC_{min}	Aggregated latency of the network
T	Lifetime of network
T_{max}	Maximum lifetime
R_{max}	Maximum transmission range
N_S	Number of nodes
$MD - i$	Maximum decrease due to removal of i nodes
$AMD - i$	Average of maximum decrease due to removal of i nodes
$MI - i$	Maximum increase due to removal of i nodes
$AMI - i$	Average of maximum increase due to removal of i nodes
Ref	Original network (<i>i.e.</i> , all nodes operating properly)
N_C	Number of critical nodes
e_i	Amount of energy stored in battery of sensor nodes

the shortest path between the sensors and the sink. This second model (Section III-B) aims to maximize the lifetime that was originally proposed in [5]. In the third and fourth models, the latency/lifetime trade-off is examined using the two previous models. Joint model 1 (Section III-C) sets minimum latency as a constraint and maximizes lifetime by increasing the relaxation factor. Model 2 (Section III-D) minimizes latency by setting the maximum lifetime as a constraint and reducing it by a relaxation factor. Section III-E describes the iterative procedure for identifying critical nodes based on these models. Table I provides a summary of the terminology and parameters used in these models.

A. Latency optimization model

The latency is assumed to be linearly proportional to the hops between the two end nodes as in [17] and this model targets minimizing the hops for all sensor-sink paths. A node-to-sink latency increase is also proportional to the number of hops from the sensor node to the sink, and the MIP model finds the path with the minimum hop count from all sensor nodes-to-sink.

In (1), the flow balancing constraint is stated: for all sensor

<p>Minimize HC Subject to:</p> $\sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} - \sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} = \begin{cases} s_i, & \forall i \in W \\ -\sum_{j \in W} s_j, & i = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$ $\sum_{i \in W} \sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} = HC \quad (2)$ $f_{ij} = 0; \text{ if } d_{ij} > R_{max}, \quad \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (3)$ $f_{ij} \geq 0, \quad \forall (i, j) \in E \quad (4)$

nodes other than the BS, the amount of data flowing out of a node equals the amount of data that it produces and receives (Incoming data flow plus self-produced data flow must

equal outgoing data flow). In addition, all generated data from the sensor nodes must terminate at the BS (*i.e.*, node n_0). Assuming that each node creates a single packet, the sum of flows gives the total hop count. Equation (2) calculates the total number of hops (*i.e.*, HC) from all sensor nodes to the BS. For instance, combining two flows from two different sources at a relay node n_i would increase the number of hops by two (flows from two other nodes) plus one (a data unit created at n_i). Equation (3) ensures that if the distance between n_i and n_j (*i.e.*, d_{ij}) is larger than transmission range at maximum power level (*i.e.*, $d_{ij} > R(l_{max})$) then these nodes cannot communicate with each other. Equation (4) ensures that all flows are non-negative.

B. Lifetime model

In this part, the model maximizes the network lifetime (T_{lt}) to achieve the longest possible network lifetime ($T_{lt_{[max]}}$).

Time is scheduled into constant duration rounds ($T_{rnd} =$

Maximize T_{lt}
Subject to:

$$\sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} - \sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} = T_{lt}, \quad \forall i \in W \quad (5)$$

$$T_{bsy,i} = T_{slt} \left[\sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} + \sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} \right] + T_{lt} T_{DA}, \quad \forall i \in W \quad (6)$$

$$\underbrace{\sum_{j \in V} E_{tx,ij}^{opt} f_{ij}}_{\text{transmission}} + \underbrace{E_{rx} \sum_{j \in W} f_{ji}}_{\text{reception}} + \underbrace{P_{slp}(T_{lt} T_{rnd} - T_{bsy,i})}_{\text{sleep}} + \underbrace{T_{lt} E_{DA}}_{\text{acquisition}} \leq e_i, \quad \forall i \in W \quad (7)$$

$$T_{slt} \left[\sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} + \sum_{j \in W} f_{ji} + \sum_{j \in W} f_{jk} I_{jk}^i \right] \leq T_{lt} T_{rnd}, \quad \forall i \in W \quad (8)$$

$$I_{jk}^i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } d_{ij} \leq \gamma R(l_{max}^{opt}) \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$e_i = \varepsilon, \quad \forall i \in W \quad (10)$$

$$f_{ij} \geq 0, \quad \forall (i,j) \in E \quad (11)$$

20s). In each round, all sensor nodes generate data and one packet is generated per time unit (*i.e.*, T_{rnd}) for all sensors. During the lifetime of a network, equation (5) is used to balance the incoming and outgoing flows. In other words, a sensor node generates T_{lt} data packets within T_{rnd} time units. We use Mica2 motes' energy dissipation characteristics for the energy consumption calculations in our model. Mica2 motes [19] consists of an Atmel Atmega 128L processor and Chipcon CC1000 radio. As represented in Table II, energy consumption for transmit power level l is denoted as $E_{tx}(l)$ and the transmission range at this level is indicated as $R(l)$.

If the distance between n_i and n_j (d_{ij}) is greater than maximum transmission range ($R_{max} = 82.92$ m), no data can be sent from n_i to n_j . Each sensor node chooses its optimal transmission energy from a finite set denoted as S_L (*i.e.*, there are just 26 power levels to choose from). At each round energy dissipation for data acquisition on each node is $E_{DA} = 57\mu J$. The power consumption for data acquisition is obtained by adding the power for running the processor ($5.4mW$) and the sensor board ($6mW$) in active mode [20], [21] (*i.e.*, $P_{DA} = 11.4mW$). E_{DA} can be obtained by multiplying P_{DA} with the total data acquisition and processing time ($T_{DA} = 5ms$). The slot time (T_{slt}) is taken as 51 ms. Total busy time in a sensor node is obtained as in Equation (6). Equation (7) states that the total energy dissipation at each node is limited by the amount of energy stored (e_i) in batteries. Energy dissipation terms on the left side of inequality in this equation account for transmission, reception, sleep, and data acquisition energies, respectively. Note that if a node is neither a receiver nor a transmitter at any slot or if it is not acquiring data then it is in the sleep mode. Power consumption in sleep mode is taken as $30\mu W$ (*i.e.*, $P_{slp} = 30\mu W$). The constraint for bandwidth is presented in Equation (8). This constraint is an abused version of the sufficient condition stated in [22], [23], [21]. In this constraint, it is guaranteed that the channel bandwidth required to perform communication operations at each node is strictly bounded by the available bandwidth. For all nodes including the BS the aggregate duration of incoming flows, outgoing flows, and interfering flows is upper bounded by the total network lifetime. We refer to the flows around node- i which are not flowing into or flowing out of node- i , however, affect the available bandwidth of node- i as interfering flows. Interference function (I_{jk}^i) is formulated in Equation (9). It claims that the flow from node- j to node- k interferes with node- i if the distance between node- j and node- k times γ is greater than or equal to the distance between node- j and node- i . According to our assumption, each sensor node except BS is assigned with equal initial energy at the beginning of the network operation as formulated in (10). Equation (11) asserts that flows must be non-negative. Each sensor needs a fixed amount of energy to receive a data packet and a specific amount of energy to send. The energy required for transmitting one bit depends on the distance between the source (n_i) and destination (n_j), the energy required for receiving one bit has a constant value ($E_{rx} = 0.923 \mu J/\text{bit}$). The optimal power level ($E_{tx,ij}^{opt}$) to transmit over a distance (d_{ij}) can be expressed as:

$$E_{tx,ij}^{opt} = \begin{cases} E_{tx}(l_{min}), & \text{if } d_{ij} \leq R(l_{min}) \\ E_{tx}^{(l)}, & \text{if } R(l-1) < d_{ij} \leq R(l) \\ \infty & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

C. Joint model 1: Relaxation of the minimum latency

In this model, we try to obtain the network lifetime T_{lt} whilst constraining the network latency. This optimization model uses all previous formulations mentioned in Section III-B along with Equation (13) which limits the total number of hops during the network lifetime. The HC_{min} is

TABLE II: Transmission energy consumption ($E_{tx}(l)$ in nJ/bit) and transmission range ($R(l)$ in m) at each power level (l) for the Mica2 motes as a function of power level [19]. Energy dissipation for reception of data is constant ($E_{rx} = 922nJ/bit$).

l	$E_{tx}(l)$	$R(l)$	l	$E_{tx}(l)$	$R(l)$
1 (l_{min})	671.88	19.3	14	843.75	41.19
2	687.50	20.46	15	867.19	43.67
3	703.13	21.69	16	1078.13	46.29
4	705.73	22.69	17	1132.81	49.07
5	710.94	24.38	18	1135.42	52.01
6	723.96	25.84	19	1179.69	55.13
7	726.56	27.39	20	1234.38	58.44
8	742.19	29.03	21	1312.50	61.95
9	757.81	30.78	22	1343.75	65.67
10	773.44	32.62	23	1445.31	69.61
11	789.06	34.58	24	1500.01	73.79
12	812.50	36.66	25	1664.06	78.22
13	828.13	38.86	26 (l_{max})	1984.38	82.92

the optimal HC value obtained using the latency optimization model, while $\lambda_{hc} \in [0, 1]$ is the relaxation factor on the hop count.

Maximize T_{lt}
 Subject to:

$$\sum_{i \in W} \sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} \leq \lambda_{hc} \times HC_{min} \times T_{lt} \quad (13)$$

Equation (5) – (11)

D. Joint model 2: Relaxation of the maximum lifetime

We also are interested in finding the minimum hop count paths that give us the maximum lifetime ($T_{lt_{[max]}}$). In this case, we change the objective function of the previous joint model from maximization of the lifetime T_{lt} to minimization of hop count (HC). Indeed this model uses all aforementioned constraints in Section III-C with the difference in types of T_{lt} and HC . In the previous model, T_{lt} is used as an integer variable but here it is an input parameter as $T_{lt_{[max]}}$, while $\lambda_{T_{lt}} \in [0, 1]$ is the relaxation factor of the lifetime. Besides, HC was an input parameter but here it is changed to a decision variable to solve our model.

Minimize HC
 Subject to:

$$\sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} - \sum_{j \in V} f_{ji} = T_{lt_{[max]}}, \quad \forall i \in V \quad (14)$$

Equation (6) – (11)

$$\sum_{i \in W} \sum_{j \in V} f_{ij} \leq \lambda_{T_{lt}} \times T_{lt_{[max]}} \times HC \quad (15)$$

E. Critical node identification

As shown in Fig. 1, identifying N_c critical nodes is an iterative process based on one of the previous models for evaluating the criticality of each node. For example, to find critical nodes solely from a latency perspective, we use the

latency model described in Section III-A. As an alternative, if the primary interest is a latency/lifetime trade-off with a relaxed minimum hop count, the joint model 1 (Section III-C) is used. According to the model to which the procedure is described, a generic term metric refers either to latency or lifetime. The procedure begins by creating network topology and calculating its reference value of metric. The metric is then computed for each possible combination of N_c nodes that were removed. After running $\binom{N_S}{N_c}$, N_c critical nodes are identified, along with performance degradation when these N_c critical nodes are removed. A similar procedure is repeated for N_R different topologies. Finally, the average performance degradations caused by critical node removals are calculated.

Fig. 1: The procedure to identify the critical nodes

IV. RESULTS

We utilized a uniform random distribution to determine the positions of sensor nodes on a circular disk-shaped network with a radius of 200 m and consisting of N_S nodes ($N_S - 1$ sensors and 1 sink). We define the initial node battery capacity of $\epsilon = 3J$. The following figures are determined considering $N_c = \{1, 2\}$. Four different results are considered:

- Maximum Increase (MI), the maximum among all maximum increases with respect to the optimal case obtained over N_R different topologies
- Average Increase (AI), the average of all maximum increases obtained over N_R different topologies
- Maximum Decrease (MD), the maximum among all maximum decreases obtained over N_R different topologies
- Average Decrease (AD), the average of all maximum decreases obtained over N_R different topologies

The results of the latency minimization problem are shown in Fig. 2, where we aim to find minimum hop count (HC_{min}) when most critical node $N_c = 1$ and second critical node $N_c = 2$ are removed from the network. Fig. 3 depicts the results for the lifetime maximization problem. In both cases,

Fig. 2: Increase in the network latency due to removal of 1 and 2 critical nodes as a function of the number of nodes.

Fig. 3: Reduction in the network lifetime, due to removal of 1 and 2 critical nodes as a function of the number of nodes.

Fig. 4: Network lifetime change (%) due to the relaxation of hop count (λ_{hc}) for $N_S = 100$.

Fig. 5: Increase in network latency due to the relaxation of lifetime ($\lambda_{T_{tt}}$) for $N_S = 100$.

results are obtained running $N_R = 100$ different network topologies. In Fig. 2, the increase in the network latency is represented for $N_S = 50, 60, 70, 80, 90$, and 100 nodes after removing the most critical node and the second most critical nodes. The figure shows that removing the critical nodes has a greater impact when there are fewer nodes in the network. The reason for this is that low-density networks offer fewer alternative paths. In these cases, the performance difference between the optimal path and the second-best alternative is substantial, and removing the critical ones results in a signif-

icant increase in latency. In a network with more nodes, the connections between the nodes become more distributed, and the network's flexibility increases, so removing crucial nodes will have less of an impact on latency. For example, disabling only 2 nodes out of 50 nodes results in an average 17% latency increase (AI-2). However, in the worst-case scenario, for $N_S = 50$, increases latency by almost 70%. It can be observed that a second node removal has less relative impact on the latency. In the scenario with $N_S = 100$ nodes, the average increase has very close behavior between $N_C = 1$ and $N_C = 2$; on the contrary, the maximum increase with $N_C = 2$ is twice the value obtained with $N_C = 1$.

In Fig. 3, the network lifetime decreases after removing one and two critical nodes is represented for the same number of nodes. As it can be seen, in the worst-case result, when removing just one node for $N_S = 50$, network lifetime is decreased by around 46%. As stated before, since networks with low density offer less number of alternative paths, it is not possible to evenly redistribute the connections and nodes that were *almost* critical are endorsed with new connections that substantially reduce their lifetime and thus, the overall network lifetime. When the number of nodes increases, the maximum lifetime decrease is lower, reaching a 29% decrease for $N_S = 100$ for the worst-case result of 1 node removal. Also, note that the difference in the average lifetime decrease achieved by the removal of the 1 and 2 nodes gap is reduced with higher node densities (a similar behavior is observed for latency increase). The reason is that as the node density increases, the number of alternative paths also increases. Results for the joint model with minimum hop count relaxation are shown both in Fig. 4. In the case of the joint model with lifetime enforcement, results are shown in Fig. 5. The curve *Ref* is obtained considering all nodes working properly and it is used as a reference. In Fig. 4, we can observe that when no relaxation is applied, AD-1 and AD-2 have the highest values, 46%, and 56% respectively. Note that these percentages represent the performance difference with respect to the optimal case without any node removal. When the hop count is relaxed by at least 24% (*i.e.*, $\lambda_{hc} \geq 1.24$), *Ref* reaches zero lifetime decrease (*i.e.*, there is no decrease in lifetime). However, this ideal situation does not happen when critical nodes are removed. In fact, for both $N_C = 1$ and $N_C = 2$ cases, the minimum AD-1 and AM-2 are 13% and 20% respectively reached when hop count relaxation is 24%. These minimum values do not change anymore (*i.e.*, asymptotic behavior) although the hop count relaxation is further increased. These results show that the effect of critical nodes can be mitigated considerably by relaxing the minimal latency objective. For example, the lifetime reduction resulting from one critical node removal is 46% for the minimum latency enforcement. However, such lifetime deterioration can be reduced to 13% by allowing the latency increase of only 24%. Hence, as the node density is reduced, the lifetime deterioration is higher with critical node elimination. This also shows the need for such relaxation especially for lower node densities. Similar behavior is observed in Fig. 5. Relaxing lifetime ($\lambda_{T_{tt}}$) by

40%, *Ref* curve reaches zero latency increase. AI-1 and AI-2 decrease their values too by relaxing lifetime but not more than 1.7% and 3.2% respectively. Imposing minimal lifetime as a constraint (*i.e.*, $\lambda_{T_{it}} = 1$) results in a 6% average latency increase for the evaluated networks. However, the removal of two critical nodes multiplies this increase (performance deterioration) by more than twice. Comparing Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, the significance of criticality is more important in the performance of network lifetime when compared to the network latency; with $N_C = 2$, lifetime decrease is 20% more than the optimal case while latency increase is only 3.2%.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a methodology for identifying the critical nodes in IoT networks that, when removed, cause the most deterioration of network latency and lifetime based on a novel MIP framework. Based on the results we have obtained, we can appreciate the importance of the critical nodes. For example in a 100-node network, if two critical nodes are removed, the lifetime can decrease up to 56% with respect to the optimal case if the minimum latency is enforced. However, such lifetime deterioration can be reduced to 13% by allowing the latency increase of 24%. All these results prove the importance of the identification of the critical nodes and in particular the numerical evaluation of their impact on the network performance. It is worth mentioning that the present methodology can also be used for any deployments (random and non-random IoT sensor locations), including intelligent transportation systems where sensors could be placed at intersections to gather real-time data on traffic flow, vehicle density, and pedestrian movement. Accordingly, the critical nodes and their impact on the overall performance can be explored.

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